

Proposed Law #117: A Law Setting Minimum Good Governance Membership Requirements for Local Chief Executives such as Mayor and Governor

Version 1.0

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1. Must have a Freedom of Information Ordinance and an Anti-Political Dynasty Ordinance. (The FOI Ordinance should be of the same quality as that of Pasig City, which includes a penalty clause. The Anti-Political Dynasty Ordinance is yet to be created.)
2. Must have a public SALN (Statement of Assets, Liabilities, and Net Worth) from the first year of being a public official up to the present (if incumbent).
3. Must have a bank secrecy waiver. (Available upon request by the Ombudsman. Making it public is optional, as it can be used politically.)
4. Must have a city, municipality, or province with adequate schools proportionate to the number of Out-of-School Youth and Adults (OSYA). (Proposed Law #2 last year)
5. Must have a public ledger of all contracts or documents signed in the conduct of duties and responsibilities. (See Proposed Law #116 or Proposed EO published on October 17)
6. Must have an ordinance requiring all elective officials to work full-time, from 8 a.m. to 5 p.m., five days a week, like ordinary employees. (Full-Time Ordinance)
7. Must have a transparent local website, similar to that of Singapore, with all legislative documents uploaded and publicized, in addition to those already required by law to be posted in public places.
8. Must have signed, publicized, and notarized an affidavit stating that all wealth in excess of Php 5 million shall be donated to the education sector, especially for building schools and providing scholarships to Filipino children. (Exemption: Wealth reported in the first SALN, or wealth justifiable by Income Tax Return)
9. Must conduct at least a two-hour public forum with his or her constituents once a month (or at least two hours per week for better public participation).

10. Must have a notarized transcript of all meetings related to his or her duties and responsibilities, to assess whether the decisions are made in the best interest of the people and the greater good.

This list and proposed law will be updated in the future.

It may also serve as a minimum requirement to join a strong political party in the Philippines.

Note: *This document presents a core idea and does not yet constitute a fully drafted proposed law with detailed sections. It is intended as a foundation for further development and refinement in future legislative work.*

The majority of the first 100 Proposed Laws are included in The Great Nation 2025 started on December 9, 2024. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5310407> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5310407>).

Additional proposed laws will be gradually added in future updates.